

Possible Antituberculous Compounds. Part XI. *N*-2-Benzothiazolyl- and *N*-3-Quinolyl-amidines

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Several *N*-2-benzothiazolyl- and *N*-3-quinolyl-amidines have been prepared with a view to studying their tuberculostatic activity.

The observation that many heterocyclic compounds like nicotinamide, *N*-thiazolyl-nicotinamide¹, isonicotinic acid hydrazide², 4-amino- α -phenylpyridine, and *N*-4-phenyl- α -pyridyl-*p*-toluamidine³ possess remarkable activity against *Mycobacterium tubercule* led us to work on heterocyclic amines, viz., 2-aminobenzothiazole and 3-aminoquinoline. These amidines were prepared by a method described earlier⁴.

These amines were converted into the corresponding ammonium benzenesulphonates and the latter on fusion with benzo-, tolu (*o*-, *m*-, *p*^{*})-, naphtho (α - & β)-, aceto-, and valero-nitriles at 200-30° afforded the corresponding amidine benzenesulphonates after repeated trituration with ether. The free amidines were obtained by the usual process of basification and isolation.

[R=Ph, tolu (*o*-, *m*-, *p*-), naphtho (α - & β -), aceto and valero]

The antitubercular activity will be reported later on.

1. *J. Org. Chem.*, 1948, 13, 834.

2. Ofte *et al.*, *Naturwiss.*, 1952, 5, 118; *Deut. Med. Woch.*, 1952, 18, 573; Fox, *Science*, 1952, 116; Bernstein *et al.*, *Amer. Rev. Tuberc.*, 1952, 65, 357.

3. Misra and Khare, *this Journal*, 1954, 31, 918.

4. Misra *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1954, 31, 918; 1960, 37, 710.

*This nitrile was treated only with *N*-2-benzothiazolylammonium benzenesulphonate.

TABLE I

N-2-Benzothiazolyl amidines.

No.	M.P.	Yield.	Appearance.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.		M.P.	Picrates.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.				Found.	Reqd.
1.	180°	50%	Black	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ S	16.80	16.60	251°	"	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₇ N ₆ S	17.90	17.42
2.	118°	60	Greenish brown	C ₁₃ H ₁₃ N ₃ S	18.10	15.73	*205-10°	"	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₇ N ₆ S	16.60	16.93
3.	* > 260°	55	Light brown	"	15.30	15.73	250°	"	"	16.80	16.93
4.	110°	70	Light grey	"	16.30	15.73	240°	"	"	15.85	16.09
5.	110°	75	Green	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₃ S	14.10	13.86	244°	"	C ₂₄ H ₁₆ O ₇ N ₆ S	15.62	16.09
6.	*114°	80	light green	"	14.30	13.86	*200-10°	"	"	19.60	20.00
7.	*140°	65	Light brown	C ₉ H ₉ N ₃ S	21.45	21.98	240-45°	"	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ O ₇ N ₆ S	17.91	18.18
8.	135°	50	"	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₃ S	17.62	18.02	245°	"	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ O ₇ N ₆ S		

*Nitrile moiety same as in Table III.

**Decompose on heating.

TABLE II

N-3-Quinolyl amidines.

*No.	M.P.	Yield.	Appearance.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.		M.P.	Picrates.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Reqd.				Found.	Reqd.
1.	270°	35%	Brown	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃	16.6	17.00	125°	"	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₇ N ₆	17.10	17.65
2.	140°	30	Dark brown	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ N ₃	15.8	16.09	220°	"	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₇ N ₆	17.30	17.14
3.	150°	60	"	"	16.5	16.09	*205°	"	"	17.50	17.14
4.	135°	40	Brown	C ₂₀ H ₁₃ N ₃	13.7	14.10	*200-20°	"	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ O ₇ N ₆	15.45	15.96
5.	170°	55	"	"	13.9	14.10	*150°	"	"	15.32	15.96
6.	*160°	45	Dark brown	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₃	22.2	22.70	175°	"	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₇ N ₆	19.80	20.28
7.	180-85°	50	Brown	C ₄ H ₇ N ₃	19.0	18.50	145°	"	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ O ₇ N ₆	18.20	18.43

* Nitrile moiety same as in Table IV.

**decompose on heating.

EXPERIMENTAL

N-2-Benzothiazolyl Ammoniumbenzenesulphonate.—To a well-stirred solution of 2-aminobenzothiazole (10 g.) in dry ether (200 ml) benzenesulphonic acid (11 g.) in absolute methanol (20 ml) was added dropwise. The ammoniumbenzenesulphonate separating was filtered and recrystallised from hot water as a white amorphous powder, m.p. 180°, yield 16 g. (Table III). (Found: N, 9.50; S, 20.20. $C_{13}H_{12}O_3N_2S_2$ requires N, 9.09; S, 20.77%).

N-2-Benzothiazolyl Amidines.—*N-2-Benzothiazolyl ammoniumbenzenesulphonate* (1.5 g.) and the corresponding nitriles (1.5 g.) were taken in a 100 ml r.b. flask, fitted with a reflux condenser and a calcium chloride guard tube and the contents heated at 200-30° (external bath temp.) for 4 to 5 hours with occasional shaking. The contents were cooled and triturated with ether when the respective amidine benzenesulphonates were obtained. The products were stirred mechanically for 4 to 5 hours with 5 *N-NaOH* (50 ml). The amidines, thus obtained, were filtered and recrystallised from chloroform-petroleum ether. The amidines were also characterised through their picrates (Table I).

TABLE III
N-2-Benzothiazolylamidine benzenesulphonates.

No.	Nitrile moiety.	M.P.	Yield.	Appearance.	Formula.
1.	Ph	134-40°	60%	Black	$C_{20}H_{17}O_3N_3S_2$
2.	<i>o</i> -Tol	151°	70	Brown	$C_{21}H_{19}O_3N_3S_2$
3.	<i>m</i> -Tol	145°	60	Light brown	"
4.	<i>p</i> -Tol	125°	80	Grey	"
5.	α -Naphthyl	150-55°	90	Dark brown	$C_{24}H_{19}O_3N_3S_2$
6.	β - "	175°	85	Dark green	"
7.	Me	155-80°	70	Whitish dark	$C_{15}H_{13}O_3N_3S_2$
8.	$CH_3(CH_2)_3$	165°	60	White	$C_{18}H_{21}O_3N_3S_2$

N-3-Quinolyl ammoniumbenzenesulphonate (A) was obtained in an analogous manner as a yellow powder, by taking 3-aminoquinoline (10 g.) m.p. 192°, yield 18 g. (Table IV). (Found: N, 9.7; S, 10.52. $C_{15}H_{14}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 9.27; S, 9.94%).

TABLE IV
N-3-Quinolylamidine benzenesulphonates.

No.	Nitrile moiety.	M.P.	Yield.	Appearance.	Formula.
1.	Ph	175-80°	55%	Black	$C_{22}H_{19}O_3N_3S$
2.	<i>o</i> -Tol	..	60	Dark brown	$C_{23}H_{21}O_3N_3S$
3.	<i>m</i> -Tol	85-90°	65	Brown	"
4.	α -Naphthyl	..	60	Black	$C_{26}H_{21}O_3N_3S$
5.	β - "	125-30°	70	Dark brown	"
6.	Me	180-85°	50	Brown	$C_{17}H_{17}O_3N_3S$
7.	$CH_3(CH_2)_3$	200-205°	60	Dark brown	$C_{20}H_{23}O_3N_3S$

N-3-Quinolylamidines were synthesised similarly by taking 1 g. each of (A) and the respective nitrile. The amidines were also characterised through their picrates (Table II).

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